

Novel topological properties and entropy studies of the rectangular oligomer hexagonal cycloarene structure

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Abstract

Topological indices are precise chemical descriptors that are highly useful in connecting molecules to their physical properties. They were discovered by using graph-theoretical techniques. In order to create cycloarenes, a subclass of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, benzene rings must be arranged in a circular pattern. These molecules have recently received a lot of attention due to their unusual electrical characteristics and pore structure, which enable their immediate practical use. In this study, we develop analytical formulations for different R, S, and Van indices of the rectangular hexagonal cycloarene structure. The validity of these indexes is then supported by the data. In order to evaluate the quantitative structure-property relationships of these compounds with different electrical and spectroscopic properties, statistical methods are also used. Instead of the commonly known concept of entropy in thermodynamics.

Keywords: Cycloarene, Shannon's entropy, Topological descriptors, Van index, S index, R index

1. Introduction

The topology subfield of mathematical chemistry makes use of the idea of chemical graph theory. It gained increased popularity as a result of the graph theory applications that its proponents showed for the mathematical modeling of chemical characteristics [1]. Chemists have discovered that a compound's molecular structure and physicochemical properties are closely related through a substantial body of experimental evidence. Later, more complex graph-theoretical techniques were developed to characterize many characteristics of chemical compounds.

The idea of topological indices, which are specific network invariants, is one such crucial tool. Due to their usage in creating quantitative structure activity (QSAR) and quantitative structure-property relationships (QSPR), which connect a substance's chemical structure to its properties [2, 3], they are becoming more and more important. The main aims of this study are the definition of defined entropies of the RHK(m,n,p) structure and the introduction of unique entropy measurements based on R, S, and Van topological indices. This makes it easier to identify the many physicochemical features of complex substances, which might be challenging to identify using experimental methods. They are frequently used

in the field of computer-assisted drug development because they maximize efficacy and cost. Numerous studies have been conducted over the years [4-6] on the mathematical development and evolution of indices that provide accurate connections between structures and their function. Due to the fusing of hexagonal carbon rings, chemical structures known as benzenoid hydrocarbon systems lack non-hexagonal interior faces [7]. Instead, a finite number of hexagonal rings are removed from the interior of a benzenoid system to produce a coronoid hydrocarbon system, and the exterior face of the system is bounded by hexagons [8]. If you want to learn more about coronoid systems and its subclasses, look through [9, 10] and the references therein. After the discovery of cycloarenes like kekulene, which are made by linear and angular annulations of benzene units, research on benzenoid and coronoid hydrocarbons began [11].

Recently, more researchers have become interested in cycloarenes like kekulene and its derivatives because of characteristics like the magnetocaloric effect caused by the presence of delocalized electrons [12]. Later, substantial theoretical and practical research on coronoid structures arose as a result of the wide variety of uses for them. Massive polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) are good examples of model molecules for graphite sheets and other carbon-based materials [13]. Their ability to accommodate metal ions and convey them is accounted for by their electrical characteristics, which are brought on by superaromaticity and the suitable pore sizes. The majority of these PAHs are byproducts of specific chemical processes involving mineral oil, some of which are especially dangerous for the environment. This necessitates a theoretical and experimental research into their features.

Recently found macrocycles called cycloarenes are made up of several benzene rings connected in a linear and angular arrangement. Following the synthesis of the first cycloarene, kekulene, in 1978, there have been several enquiries and additional studies into the conjugation of macrocycles. A number of facts regarding the electrical and magnetic properties of this particular family of PAH were supported by similar cycloarene septulene [14]. Numerous studies are currently being done to comprehend these compounds' superaromaticity, which explains how macrocyclic conjugation increases their thermodynamic stability [15]. It is clear that research utilizing a variety of topological methodologies assisted in the analysis of a number of electronic features, including the delocalization of pi-electrons. In situations where experimental and quantum chemical methods are challenging to use, graph-theoretical techniques paired with topological investigations of the molecular structure have given researchers tools to assess a variety of broader PAH features [16, 17].

To characterize and assess the numerous physicochemical properties of these recently created substances, methodologies based on combinatorics and graph theory as well as computer-aided simulations are required. For the creation of reliable QSAR and QSPR models, accurate and generalized topological quantities must be applied. Topological indices, which evaluate the structural specifics of complex substances using the idea of molecular graphs, offer helpful approaches to detect and connect various properties in this context. The complexity of a molecule is measured by information-theoretical entropy, which has been shown to be highly associated with thermodynamic entropy values. It can therefore be utilized to spot the phase change between two large molecular formations. The topological technique and graph theory have been used to quantify the chemical spectrum, conjugation, and aromaticity of molecules [16, 18–21]. The literature has already provided topological characterization for a large number of benzenoid and coronoid hydrocarbons [6, 16, 21–24].

Cycloarenes like kekulene and its enormous oligomers have recently received a lot of attention due to their cyclic conjugation and D_{6h} symmetry. The resemblance between these structures' symmetry and the D_6

symmetric group reveals the mathematical significance of these structures. For simple cycloarenes and kekulene oligomers, the computation of degree- and distance-based topological indices has already been completed [6, 21, 25]. This problem still persists for big D_{6h} symmetric cycloarene compounds with additional benzene rings and associated oligomers, which is what motivates our research. The main objective of this work is to select significant degree- and degree sum-based indices that may reliably predict the features of D_{6h} symmetric cycloarenes with varying pore sizes and related oligomers. Computational complexity can be lowered by removing additional indices with a weaker chemical applicability. We shall study in detail a variety of large polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons with hollow sites and total hexagon ring condensation. In the current work, specific attention is paid to the general D_{6h} -symmetric cycloarenes denoted by $CY(p)$, where p is the number of benzene rings on one side of the cycloarene's perimeter. Without also losing their D_{6h} symmetric cycloarene structure, kekulene oligomers prevent the investigation of the consequences of extra benzene rings introduced to their peripheral. An extensive assessment of the literature served as the basis for the current work [16]. The only driving force behind the parameter p is theoretical interest in creating large cavity coronoids, as stated in [16]. Cycloarenes, commonly known as super-rings, are the building blocks of enormous structures with certain pore widths. Topological index values and information entropy values for Kekulene and its tessellations have already been determined [6, 16, 26]. We also provide expanded relations for computing various topological indices for universal D_{6h} symmetric cycloarenes and their hexagonal and rectangular oligomers, as well as numerical entropy analyses with graphical comparisons. The new discoveries made here are now a specific instance of the earlier findings. We gathered data on numerous chemical characteristics of these substances produced utilizing experimental and quantum chemistry methods in order to illustrate the importance of the theory. The accuracy of the indices and their applicability to the nearby structures were then assessed using correlation analysis. Our proposed stability study of diverse oligomers using information entropy as a workable substitute for standard thermodynamic entropy extends the interdisciplinary relationship between graph theory and chemistry. For topological characterization, three different framework types for the generalized super-ring $CY(p)$ are considered. By encircling $CY(p)$ by itself, it is feasible to produce the zigzag hexagonal cycloarene system. In the center of a rectangle hexagonal oligomer, a zigzag hexagonal structure is anchored, and $CY(p)$ molecules are connected between each pair of super rings on its six sides in a pyramidal arrangement. As additional $CY(p)$ molecules are fused in between these pyramidal structures, the structure eventually assumes a hexagonal form. A rectangular hexagonal oligomer structure with n circular $CY(p)$ layers is known as $RHK(m,n,p)$. The carbon frameworks of the $RHK(m,n,p)$ configurations are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1 RHK(m,n,p) cycloarene oligomer growth patterns

2. Computational methods

Throughout the work, we shall refer to the D_{6h} symmetric polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons as simple graph G . The edges of the graph G , or $E(G)$, are the C-C bonds, while the vertices of the graph $V(G)$ are the carbon atoms that make up the coronoid system. The expression $e=uv$ designates the edge connecting the vertices u and v . $deg(u)$, the degree of the vertex u in the graph G , stands for the number of other carbon atoms to which a carbon atom u is attached. We will now discuss various graph-theoretical methods employed in our research using this model. $N(v)$ is the set of all neighbouring vertices of v . The sum degree of the vertex v , denoted as S_v , is the total number of all the degrees of neighbouring vertices of v . The multiplication degree of the vertex v , denoted as M_v , is the multiplication of total number of all the degrees of neighbouring vertices of v . Van degree of the vertex v , defined as; $van(v) = \frac{S_v}{M_v}$ [27]. Also, reverse Van degree of the vertex v , defined as; $rvan(v) = \frac{M_v}{S_v}$. Van topological indices defined as [27];

The first Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} van(v)^2$.

The second Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} van(u)van(v)$.

The third Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [van(u) + van(v)]$.

The first reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rvan(v)^2$.

The second reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rvan(u)rvan(v)$.

The third reverse Van index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $Van^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rvan(u) + rvan(v)]$.

R degree of the vertex v , defined as; $r(v) = M_v + S_v$ [28]. Also, reverse R degree of the vertex v , defined as; $rr(v) = \frac{1}{M_v + S_v}$. R topological indices defined as [28]:

The first R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} r(v)^2$.

The second R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} r(u)r(v)$.

The third R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [r(u) + r(v)]$.

The first reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rr(v)^2$.

The second reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rr(u)rr(v)$.

The third reverse R index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $R^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rr(u) + rr(v)]$.

S degree of the vertex v , defined as; $s(v) = |M_v - S_v|$ [29]. Also, reverse S degree of the vertex v , defined as; $rs(v) = \frac{1}{|M_v - S_v| + 1}$. R topological indices defined as [29]:

The first S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^1(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} s(v)^2$.

The second S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} s(u)s(v)$.

The third S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [s(u) + s(v)]$.

The first reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^{1r}(G) = \sum_{v \in V(G)} rs(v)^2$.

The second reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rs(u)rs(v)$.

The third reverse S index of a simple connected graph G defined as; $S^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} [rs(u) + rs(v)]$.

Mathematicians can use graph entropy measurements, which are split into intrinsic and extrinsic measures, to relate graph components like edges and vertices with probability distributions. The application of graph entropies is widespread in many academic fields, including chemistry, ecology, sociology, and biology [30,31]. Dehmer created, assessed, and published information functional-based graph entropies [32,33]. Estrada et al.'s [34] definition of graph entropy is valid from a physical perspective in addition to their analysis of the walk-based graph entropies. Determining a quantitative definition of a molecular structure and examining the biological and chemical properties of molecular graphs are two applications for entropy network measurements [35]. There are numerous uses for entropy measures in the analysis of chemical graphs. They are used to examine the chemical characteristics of complex networks. The Shannon's entropy definition for 2D networks based on the topological index T is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{Entropy}_T(G) &= \mathbf{Ent}_T(G) \\ &= \log(T(G)) - \frac{1}{T(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv)) \end{aligned}$$

where f is the topological index's structural-functional identifier. In the case of the second Van index, for instance

$f(uv) = \mathbf{van}(u)\mathbf{van}(v)$ and in the case of the third Van index, for instance $f(uv) = \mathbf{van}(u) + \mathbf{van}(v)$.

3. Main results

In this section, we first determine the Van, R, and S topological indices for RHK(m,n,p) families, followed by the associated entropies of these indices. As shown in Fig. 2, fix a super-ring in the center with a benzene p number on one side and let n to be the dimension of hexagonal oligomers.

$RHK(m,n,p)$ families have the following sum, multiplication edge end vertex degree and Van degree partitions which are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Edge end vertex sum, multiplication degree and Van degree partition of $RHK(m,n,p)$.

Cardinality	(S_u, S_v)	(M_u, M_v)	$(van(u), van(v))$	$(rvan(u), rvan(v))$
$2m + 4n$	(5,5)	(6,6)	(5/6,5/6)	(6/5,6/5)
$4m + 8n$	(5,7)	(6,12)	(5/6,7/12)	(6/5,12/7)
$4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp)$	(6,7)	(9,12)	(2/3,7/12)	(3/2,12/7)
$4(6mn - n - 2m)$	(6,8)	(9,18)	(2/3,4/9)	(3/2,9/4)
$(p - 3)(n - m + 6mn)$	(7,7)	(12,12)	(7/12,7/12)	(12/7,12/7)
$4m + 8n$	(7,8)	(12,18)	(7/12,4/9)	(12/7,9/4)
$2(12mn - 4n - 5m)$	(8,8)	(18,18)	(4/9,4/9)	(9/4,9/4)

$RHK(m,n,p)$ families have the following R and S degree partitions which are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 S and R edge end vertex degree partition of $RHK(m,n,p)$.

Cardinality	$(s(u), s(v))$	$(rs(u), rs(v))$	$(r(u), r(v))$	$(rr(u), rr(v))$
$2m + 4n$	(1,1)	(1/2,1/2)	(11,11)	(1/11,1/11)
$4m + 8n$	(1,5)	(1/2,1/6)	(11,19)	(1/11,1/19)
$4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp)$	(3,5)	(1/4,1/6)	(15,19)	(1/15,1/19)
$4(6mn - n - 2m)$	(3,10)	(1/4,1/11)	(15,26)	(1/15,1/26)
$(p - 3)(n - m + 6mn)$	(5,5)	(1/6,1/6)	(19,19)	(1/19,1/19)
$4m + 8n$	(5,10)	(1/6,1/11)	(19,26)	(1/19,1/26)
$2(12mn - 4n - 5m)$	(10,10)	(1/11,1/11)	(26,26)	(1/26,1/26)

3.1 Topological indices $RHK(m,n,p)$

The following theorems give the overall Van, R, and S indices representation of $RHK(m,n,p)$.

Theorem 1. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the second Van index of G is;

$$Van^2(G) = \frac{91}{8}mnp - \frac{4811}{216}mn - \frac{91}{48}mp + \frac{91}{48}np + \frac{9419}{1296}m + \frac{4405}{1296}n$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} van(u)van(v)$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^2(G) &= (2m + 4n) \times \frac{5}{6} \times \frac{5}{6} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{5}{6} \times \frac{7}{12} + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np \\ &+ 6mnp) \times \frac{2}{3} \times \frac{7}{12} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{2}{3} \times \frac{4}{9} + (p - 3)(n - m \\ &+ 6mn) \times \frac{7}{12} \times \frac{7}{12} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{7}{12} \times \frac{4}{9} + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{4}{9} \times \frac{4}{9} \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 2. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the second reverse Van index of G is;

$$Van^{2r}(G) = \frac{3888}{49}mnp - \frac{3483}{98}mn - \frac{648}{49}mp + \frac{648}{49}np - \frac{11061}{9800}m - \frac{24534}{1225}n$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rvan(u)rvan(v)$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^{2r}(G) &= (2m + 4n) \times \frac{6}{5} \times \frac{6}{5} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{6}{5} \times \frac{12}{7} + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + \\ &6mnp) \times \frac{3}{2} \times \frac{12}{7} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{3}{2} \times \frac{9}{4} + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \frac{12}{7} \times \frac{12}{7} + (4m + \\ &8n) \times \frac{12}{7} \times \frac{9}{4} + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{9}{4} \times \frac{9}{4} \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 3. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the third Van index of G is;

$$Van^3(G(m, n)) = 37mnp - 63mn - \frac{37}{6}mp + \frac{37}{6}np + \frac{113}{6}m + \frac{37}{6}n$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (van(u) + van(v))$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^3(G) &= (2m + 4n) \times \left(\frac{5}{6} + \frac{5}{6}\right) + (4m + 8n) \times \left(\frac{5}{6} + \frac{7}{12}\right) + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np \\ &+ 6mnp) \times \left(\frac{2}{3} + \frac{7}{12}\right) + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \left(\frac{2}{3} + \frac{4}{9}\right) + (p - 3)(n - m \\ &+ 6mn) \times \left(\frac{7}{12} + \frac{7}{12}\right) + (4m + 8n) \times \left(\frac{7}{12} + \frac{4}{9}\right) + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \left(\frac{4}{9} + \frac{4}{9}\right) \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 4. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the third reverse Van index of G is;

$$Van^{3r}(G) = \frac{18981}{49}mnp - \frac{68337}{98}mn - \frac{6327}{98}mp + \frac{6327}{98}np + \frac{79293}{490}m - \frac{24513}{980}n$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Van^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rvan(u) + rvan(v))$$

As a result by using Table 2;

$$\begin{aligned} Van^{3r}(G) &= (2m + 4n) \times \left(\frac{6}{5} + \frac{6}{5}\right) + (4m + 8n) \times \left(\frac{6}{5} + \frac{12}{7}\right) + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + \\ &6mnp) \times \left(\frac{3}{2} + \frac{12}{7}\right) + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \left(\frac{3}{2} + \frac{9}{4}\right) + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \left(\frac{12}{7} + \frac{12}{7}\right) + \\ &(4m + 8n) \times \left(\frac{12}{7} + \frac{9}{4}\right) + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \left(\frac{9}{4} + \frac{9}{4}\right) \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 5. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the second S index of G is;

$$S^2(G) = 510mnp + 1590mn - 85mp + \frac{6327}{98}np - 703m - 611n$$

Proof. Considering that is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} s(u)s(v)$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned} S^2(G) &= (2m + 4n) \times 1 \times 1 + (4m + 8n) \times 1 \times 5 + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + \\ &6mnp) \times 3 \times 5 + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times 3 \times 10 + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times 5 \times 5 + (4m + \\ &8n) \times 5 \times 10 + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times 10 \times 10 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 6. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the second reverse S index of G is;

$$S^{2r}(G) = \frac{7}{6}mnp - \frac{667}{242}mn - \frac{7}{36}mp + \frac{7}{36}np + \frac{2003}{1452}m + \frac{2005}{1452}n$$

Proof. Considering that is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^{2r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rs(u)rs(v)$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$S^{2r}(G) = (2m + 4n) \times \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{2} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{1}{2} \times \frac{1}{6} + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{1}{6} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{1}{4} \times \frac{1}{11} + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{6} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{1}{6} \times \frac{1}{11} + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{1}{11} \times \frac{1}{11}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 7. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the third S index of G is;

$$S^3(G) = 252mnp + 36mn - 42mp + 42np - 58m - 98n$$

Proof. Considering that is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (s(u) + s(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$S^3(G) = (2m + 4n) \times (1 + 1) + (4m + 8n) \times (1 + 5) + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times (3 + 5) + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times (3 + 10) + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times (5 + 5) + (4m + 8n) \times (5 + 10) + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times (10 + 10)$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 8. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the third reverse S index of G is;

$$S^{3r}(G) = 12mnp - \frac{258}{11}mn - 2mp + 2np + \frac{97}{11}m + \frac{65}{11}n$$

Proof. Considering that is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$S^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rs(u) + rs(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$S^{3r}(G) = (2m + 4n) \times \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}\right) + (4m + 8n) \times \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{6}\right) + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{6}\right) + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \left(\frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{11}\right) + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{6}\right) + (4m + 8n) \times \left(\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{11}\right) + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \left(\frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{11}\right)$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 9. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the second R index of G is;

$$R^2(G) = \frac{7}{6}mnp - \frac{667}{242}mn - \frac{7}{36}mp + \frac{7}{36}np + \frac{2003}{1452}m + \frac{2005}{1452}n$$

Proof. Considering that is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^2(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} r(u)r(v)$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned} R^2(G) &= (2m + 4n) \times 11 \times 11 + (4m + 8n) \times 11 \times 19 \\ &\quad + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times 15 \times 19 + 4(6mn - n \\ &\quad - 2m) \times 15 \times 26 + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times 19 \times 19 + (4m + 8n) \times 19 \times 26 \\ &\quad + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times 26 \times 26 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 10. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the second reverse R index of is;

$$R^{2r}(G) = \frac{182}{1805}mnp - \frac{62672}{305045}mn - \frac{91}{5415}mp + \frac{91}{5415}np + \frac{5382261}{73820890}m + \frac{318121}{7382089}n$$

Proof. Considering that is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^{2r}(G(m, n)) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} rr(u)rr(v)$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned} R^{2r}(G) &= (2m + 4n) \times \frac{1}{11} \times \frac{1}{11} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{1}{11} \times \frac{1}{19} \\ &\quad + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \frac{1}{15} \times \frac{1}{19} + 4(6mn - n \\ &\quad - 2m) \times \frac{1}{15} \times \frac{1}{26} + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \frac{1}{19} \times \frac{1}{19} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{1}{19} \times \frac{1}{26} \\ &\quad + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{1}{26} \times \frac{1}{26} \end{aligned}$$

And the conclusion follows.

Theorem 11. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, the third R index of G is;

$$R^3(G) = 1044mnp - 900mn - 174mp + 174np + 154m - 142n$$

Proof. Considering that Gis a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$R^3(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (r(u) + r(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned}
 R^3(G) &= (2m + 4n) \times (11 + 11) + (4m + 8n) \times (11 + 19) \\
 &\quad + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times (15 + 19) + 4(6mn - n \\
 &\quad - 2m) \times (15 + 26) + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times (19 + 19) \\
 &\quad + (4m + 8n) \times (19 + 26) + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times (26 + 26)
 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

Theorem 12. Let G be a $RHK(m,n,p)$ network. Then, the third reverse R index of G is;

$$R^{3r}(G) = \frac{332}{95} mnp - \frac{7552}{1235} mn - \frac{166}{285} mp + \frac{166}{285} np + \frac{78106}{40755} m + \frac{31604}{40755} n$$

Proof. Considering that is a $RHK(m,n,p)$ network. By definition;

$$R^{3r}(G) = \sum_{uv \in E(G)} (rr(u) + rr(v))$$

As a result by using Table 3;

$$\begin{aligned}
 R^{3r}(G) &= (2m + 4n) \times \left(\frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{11}\right) + (4m + 8n) \times \left(\frac{1}{11} + \frac{1}{19}\right) \\
 &\quad + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \left(\frac{1}{15} + \frac{1}{19}\right) + 4(6mn - n \\
 &\quad - 2m) \times \left(\frac{1}{15} + \frac{1}{26}\right) + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \left(\frac{1}{19} + \frac{1}{19}\right) \\
 &\quad + (4m + 8n) \times \left(\frac{1}{19} + \frac{1}{26}\right) + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \left(\frac{1}{26} + \frac{1}{26}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

the conclusion follows.

3.2 Entropies of $RHK(m,n,p)$

The following theorems give the overall entropies which are based on Van, R , and S indices representation of $RHK(m,n,p)$.

Theorem 13. Let G be a $RHK(m,n,p)$ network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the second Van index of is;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ent_{Van^2}(G) = & \log \left(\frac{91}{8} mnp - \frac{4811}{216} mn - \frac{91}{48} mp + \frac{91}{48} np + \frac{9419}{1296} m + \frac{4405}{1296} n \right) \\
 & - \frac{1}{\frac{91}{8} mnp - \frac{4811}{216} mn - \frac{91}{48} mp + \frac{91}{48} np + \frac{9419}{1296} m + \frac{4405}{1296} n} \left((2m \right. \\
 & + 4n) \times \frac{25}{36} \times \log \frac{25}{36} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{35}{72} \times \log \frac{35}{72} + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp \\
 & + np + 6mnp) \times \frac{7}{18} \times \log \frac{7}{18} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{8}{27} \times \log \frac{8}{27} + (p - 3)(n \\
 & - m + 6mn) \times \frac{49}{144} \times \log \frac{49}{144} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{7}{27} \times \log \frac{7}{27} \\
 & \left. + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{16}{81} \times \log \frac{16}{81} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^2}(G) = \log(Van^2(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^2(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 1, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 14. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the second reverse Van index of is;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ent_{Van^{2r}}(G) = & \log \left(\frac{3888}{49} mnp - \frac{3483}{98} mn - \frac{648}{49} mp + \frac{648}{49} np - \frac{11061}{9800} m - \frac{24534}{1225} n \right) - \\
 & \frac{1}{\frac{3888}{49} mnp - \frac{3483}{98} mn - \frac{648}{49} mp + \frac{648}{49} np - \frac{11061}{9800} m - \frac{24534}{1225} n} \left((2m + 4n) \times \frac{36}{25} \times \log \frac{36}{25} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{72}{35} \times \log \frac{72}{35} + \right. \\
 & 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \frac{18}{7} \times \log \frac{18}{7} \\
 & + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \frac{27}{8} \times \log \frac{27}{8} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{144}{49} \times \log \frac{144}{49} + (4m \\
 & + 8n) \times \frac{27}{7} \times \log \frac{27}{7} \\
 & \left. + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{81}{16} \times \log \frac{81}{16} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^{2r}}(G) = \log(Van^{2r}(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^{2r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 2, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 15. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the third Van index of is;

$$\begin{aligned}
 Ent_{Van^3}(G) = & \log \left(37mnp - 63mn - \frac{37}{6} mp + \frac{37}{6} np + \frac{113}{6} m + \frac{37}{6} n \right) - \\
 & \frac{1}{37mnp - 63mn - \frac{37}{6} mp + \frac{37}{6} np + \frac{113}{6} m + \frac{37}{6} n} \left((2m + 4n) \times \frac{5}{3} \times \log \frac{5}{3} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{17}{12} \times \log \frac{17}{12} + 4(4m - n - \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \frac{5}{4} \times \log \frac{5}{4} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{10}{9} \times \log \frac{10}{9} + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \frac{7}{6} \times \log \frac{7}{6} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{37}{36} \times \log \frac{37}{36} + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{8}{9} \times \log \frac{8}{9}$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^3}(G) = \log(Van^3(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^3(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 3, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 16. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the third reverse Van index of is;

$$Ent_{Van^{3r}}(G) = \log \left(\frac{18981}{49} mnp - \frac{68337}{98} mn - \frac{6327}{98} mp + \frac{6327}{98} np + \frac{79293}{490} m - \frac{24513}{980} n \right) - \frac{1}{\frac{18981}{49} mnp - \frac{68337}{98} mn - \frac{6327}{98} mp + \frac{6327}{98} np + \frac{79293}{490} m - \frac{24513}{980} n} \left((2m + 4n) \times \frac{12}{5} \times \log \frac{12}{5} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{102}{35} \times \log \frac{102}{35} + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \frac{45}{14} \times \log \frac{45}{14} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{15}{4} \times \log \frac{15}{4} + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \frac{24}{7} \times \log \frac{24}{7} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{111}{28} \times \log \frac{111}{28} + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{9}{2} \times \log \frac{9}{2} \right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{Van^{3r}}(G) = \log(Van^{3r}(G)) - \frac{1}{Van^{3r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 4, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 17. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the second S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^2}(G) = \log \left(510mnp + 1590mn - 85mp + \frac{6327}{98} np - 703m - 611n \right) - \frac{1}{510mnp + 1590mn - 85mp + \frac{6327}{98} np - 703m - 611n} \left((4m + 8n) \times 5 \times \log 5 + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times 15 \times \log 15 + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times 30 \times \log 30 + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times 25 \times \log 5 + (4m + 8n) \times 50 \times \log 50 + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times 100 \times \log 100 \right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^2}(G) = \log(S^2(G)) - \frac{1}{S^2(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 5, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 18. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the second reverse S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^{2r}}(G) = \log \left(\frac{7}{6} mnp - \frac{667}{242} mn - \frac{7}{36} mp + \frac{7}{36} np + \frac{2003}{1452} m + \frac{2005}{1452} n \right) - \frac{1}{\frac{7}{6} mnp - \frac{667}{242} mn - \frac{7}{36} mp + \frac{7}{36} np + \frac{2003}{1452} m + \frac{2005}{1452} n} \left((2m + 4n) \times \frac{1}{4} \times \log \frac{1}{4} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{1}{12} \times \log \frac{1}{12} + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \frac{1}{24} \times \log \frac{1}{24} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{1}{44} \times \log \frac{1}{44} + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \frac{1}{36} \times \log \frac{1}{36} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{1}{66} \times \log \frac{1}{66} + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{1}{121} \times \log \frac{1}{121} \right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^{2r}}(G) = \log(S^{2r}(G)) - \frac{1}{S^{2r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 6, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 19. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the third S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^3}(G) = \log(252mnp + 36mn - 42mp + 42np - 58m - 98n) - \frac{1}{252mnp + 36mn - 42mp + 42np - 58m - 98n} \left((2m + 4n) \times 2 \times \log 2 + (4m + 8n) \times 6 \times \log 6 + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times 8 \times \log 8 + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times 13 \times \log 13 + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times 10 \times \log 10 + (4m + 8n) \times 15 \times \log 15 + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times 20 \times \log 20 \right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^3}(G) = \log(S^3(G)) - \frac{1}{S^3(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 7, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 20. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the third reverse S index of is;

$$Ent_{S^{3r}}(G) = \log \left(12mnp - \frac{258}{11} mn - 2mp + 2np + \frac{97}{11} m + \frac{65}{11} n \right) - \frac{1}{12mnp - \frac{258}{11} mn - 2mp + 2np + \frac{97}{11} m + \frac{65}{11} n} \left((4m + 8n) \times \frac{2}{3} \times \log \frac{2}{3} + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \frac{5}{12} \times \log \frac{5}{12} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{15}{44} \times \log \frac{15}{44} + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \frac{1}{3} \times \log \frac{1}{3} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{17}{66} \times \log \frac{17}{66} + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{2}{11} \times \log \frac{2}{11} \right)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{S^3r}(G) = \log(S^{3r}(G)) - \frac{1}{S^{3r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 8, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 21. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the second R index of is;

$$Ent_{R^2}(G) = \log\left(\frac{7}{6}mnp - \frac{667}{242}mn - \frac{7}{36}mp + \frac{7}{36}np + \frac{2003}{1452}m + \frac{2005}{1452}n\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{7}{6}mnp - \frac{667}{242}mn - \frac{7}{36}mp + \frac{7}{36}np + \frac{2003}{1452}m + \frac{2005}{1452}n} ((2m + 4n) \times 121 \times \log 121 + (4m + 8n) \times 209 \times \log 209 + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times 285 \times \log 285 + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times 390 \times \log 390 + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times 361 \times \log 361 + (4m + 8n) \times 494 \times \log 494 + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times 676 \times \log 676)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{R^2}(G) = \log(R^2(G)) - \frac{1}{R^2(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 9, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 22. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the second reverse R index of is;

$$Ent_{R^{2r}}(G) = \log\left(\frac{182}{1805}mnp - \frac{62672}{305045}mn - \frac{91}{5415}mp + \frac{91}{5415}np + \frac{5382261}{73820890}m + \frac{318121}{7382089}n\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{182}{1805}mnp - \frac{62672}{305045}mn - \frac{91}{5415}mp + \frac{91}{5415}np + \frac{5382261}{73820890}m + \frac{318121}{7382089}n} ((2m + 4n) \times \frac{1}{121} \times \log \frac{1}{121} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{1}{209} \times \log \frac{1}{209} + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \frac{1}{285} \times \log \frac{1}{285} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{1}{390} \times \log \frac{1}{390} + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \frac{1}{361} \times \log \frac{1}{361} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{1}{494} \times \log \frac{1}{494} + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{1}{676} \times \log \frac{1}{676})$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{R^{2r}}(G) = \log(R^{2r}(G)) - \frac{1}{R^{2r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 10, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 23. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network . Then, entropy of G which is based on the third R index of is;

$$Ent_{R^3}(G) = \log(1044mnp - 900mn - 174mp + 174np + 154m - 142n) - \frac{1}{1044mnp - 900mn - 174mp + 174np + 154m - 142n} ((2m + 4n) \times 22 \times \log 22 + (4m + 8n) \times 30 \times \log 30 + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times 34 \times \log 34 + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times 41 \times \log 41 + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times 38 \times \log 38 + (4m + 8n) \times 45 \times \log 45 + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times 52 \times \log 52)$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{R^3}(G) = \log(R^3(G)) - \frac{1}{R^3(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 11, the conclusion follows.

Theorem 24. Let G be a RHK(m,n,p) network. Then, entropy of G which is based on the third reverse R index of is;

$$Ent_{R^{3r}}(G) = \log\left(\frac{332}{95}mnp - \frac{7552}{1235}mn - \frac{166}{285}mp + \frac{166}{285}np + \frac{78106}{40755}m + \frac{31604}{40755}n\right) - \frac{1}{\frac{332}{95}mnp - \frac{7552}{1235}mn - \frac{166}{285}mp + \frac{166}{285}np + \frac{78106}{40755}m + \frac{31604}{40755}n} ((2m + 4n) \times \frac{2}{11} \times \log \frac{2}{11} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{30}{209} \times \log \frac{30}{209} + 4(4m - n - 18mn - mp + np + 6mnp) \times \frac{34}{285} \times \log \frac{34}{285} + 4(6mn - n - 2m) \times \frac{41}{390} \times \log \frac{41}{390} + (p - 3)(n - m + 6mn) \times \frac{2}{19} \times \log \frac{2}{19} + (4m + 8n) \times \frac{45}{494} \times \log \frac{45}{494} + 2(12mn - 4n - 5m) \times \frac{1}{13} \times \log \frac{1}{13})$$

Proof. Considering that G is a RHK(m,n,p) network. By definition;

$$Ent_{R^{3r}}(G) = \log(R^{3r}(G)) - \frac{1}{R^{3r}(G)} \sum_{uv \in E(G)} f(uv) \log(f(uv))$$

As a result by using Theorem 12, the conclusion follows.

4. Conclusions

This work describes the generalized mathematical equation for R, S, and Van topological indices for structures of RHK(m,n,p). These generalized mathematical formulations give information-theoretic entropy measurements of several phases of 2D materials of RHK(m,n,p). It was discovered that the structures we looked at here have very little variety in their entropies. Using our suggested topological indices and entropy metrics, we may anticipate the thermochemistry, physicochemical properties, electrical, optical, and mechanical features of these numerous RHK(m,n,p) phases. These indices can also be paired with metrics from quantum chemistry, such as molecular hardness, polarizability measurements, atomic charges, etc., to build a platform that is effective for forecasting molecular connections and electronic-based properties. The same method is used to generate a large number of probabilistic entropy measurements.

Declarations

Funding: There is no funding for this research.

Competing interests: The authors declares no competing interests.

Ethics approval: Not applicable.

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